

Workshop**Advancing Skills in Liver Transplantation: A Workshop for Transplant Coordinators held in Hyderabad**

Jaya Jairam, Hemal Kanvinde
MOHAN Foundation, India

Transplant coordinators, including clinical coordinators specializing in liver transplantation, were given an opportunity to improve their knowledge through a comprehensive one-day workshop under the aegis of the LTSI Conference in Hyderabad. The workshop was organised by NATCO and MOHAN Foundation on Nov 29, 2024, at the Novotel Convention Centre, HITEC City, Hyderabad. During the inauguration, Dr. Ravi Mohanka and Dr. Abhideep Choudhury urged the transplant coordinators to improve their skills and write articles to

Dr. Mohamed Rela (4th from left), President of LTSI and other office bearers at the inauguration

showcase their work. Dr. Mohamed Rela, President of the Liver Transplant Society of India (LTSI), made a significant announcement, pledging to make transplant coordinators a specific category within the organization, further recognising their pivotal role in the transplant ecosystem.

Key Highlights of the Workshop:

The workshop covered a broad spectrum of topics and facilitated presentation and discussions amongst the transplant coordinators and experts, as follows:

- Evaluation of a liver donor
- Post liver transplant protocols
- Establishing liver transplant system in Tier II cities in India
- Documentation in international patients
- International organ allocation policies

National State-Based Liver Allocation Practices

Mrs. Arati Gokhale, Chief Coordinator of ZTCC Pune, opened the discussion by outlining the guidelines established by NOTTO, offering a national framework for organ allocation.

The allocation policies for liver for the following states were discussed in detail :

The session highlighted the organ-sharing mechanisms and the criteria for prioritizing patients on the urgent and supra-urgent lists. This interactive session shed light on the diversity of practices across the country while emphasizing the need for standardized, transparent, and ethical allocation policies.

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| • Andhra Pradesh | • Karnataka |
| • Telangana | • NCR |
| • Maharashtra | • Kerala |
| • Gujarat | • Tamil Nadu |

From Legality to Autonomy: Amplifying Living Donor Voices

The session moderated by Dr. Sonal Asthana, Lead Consultant, HPB and Liver Transplant Surgery, Aster Hospitals, Bengaluru was a compelling exploration of the rights, challenges, and experiences of living organ donors. The esteemed panel included:

- Dr. Viniyendra Pamecha, Head - Liver Transplant, ILBS, Delhi
- Dr. Gomathy Narasimhan, Senior Consultant, Multi-Organ Transplant, Dr Rela Institute and Medical Center, Chennai
- Mr. Girish Shetty, Senior Transplant Coordinator, Apollo Hospitals, Hyderabad
- Prof. (Dr.) G. B. Reddy, Legal Expert, Hyderabad
- Mrs. P.R.L. Kiranmai, Liver donor, Hyderabad
- Ms. Jaya Jairam, Project Director, MOHAN Foundation, Mumbai

The session opened with a poignant video featuring Ms. Sudha Bhamidipati, who shared her journey as a liver donor for her husband, setting an empathetic tone for the discussion.

Dr. Sonal posed incisive questions to the panel - presence of independent living donor advocates, timing and role of psychological counseling in the evaluation process, rights of living donors. Dr. Gomathy shared insights from her research on gender disparities among living liver donors, drawing data from two major Indian registries. The session highlighted the importance of recognizing and amplifying donor voices, fostering discussions that advance both ethical practices and donor well-being.

Case studies - Coordination in Liver Transplantation

Dr. Gomathy Narasimhan concluded the event with an engaging session centered on three complex case studies in liver transplantation. These included scenarios involving a marginal donor, a split liver donation, and managing the varied expectations of different surgeons. In an interactive approach, Dr. Gomathy invited delegates to role-play the scenarios, encouraging them to step into the shoes of coordinators and decision-makers. This dynamic format sparked lively discussions and active participation, providing valuable insights into real-world challenges and solutions in liver transplantation coordination. The session was a standout, leaving the audience enriched with practical knowledge and collaborative strategies.

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sunil Shroff,
MOHAN Foundation, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India
Email: shroff@mohanfoundation.org

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